

Chemistry of Valeranone¹

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Valeranone (1), the first of the unique group of sesquiterpenoid ketones, with two angular substituents in the decalin ring system, to be isolated, occurs² widely in members of the valerianaceous family. Other members, isolated later, are represented by (2), (3), (4) and (5).

Initial investigations by Govindachari *et al.*^{2b,3} and further experiments of Sorm and coworkers⁴ and of Takemoto *et al.*^{8, 9, 14} led to the elucidation of the structure and configuration of valeranone. Analytical results on valeranone and its derivatives were consistent with the molecular formula, $C_{15}H_{26}O$. Wolff-Kishner reduction of valeranone to yield the saturated hydrocarbon, valerane, $C_{15}H_{26}$ (6), indicated it to be a saturated bicyclic ketone. The same hydrocarbon was also obtained by desulphurisation of the ethylene thio-ketal of valeranone. Reduction of valeranone with lithium aluminium hydride afforded two isomeric alcohols (7), dehydrogenation of which by heating with Palladium catalyst at $320-40^{\circ}$ led to the formation of azulenic hydrocarbons, different from those obtained from known sesquiterpenoids. Further, dehydration of valeranol gave valerene (8), which on hydrogenation furnished the hydrocarbon, valerane (6).

The carbonyl stretching band at 1699 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum of valeranone was indicative of a 2,2-dialkylcyclohexanone system. Formation of an equatorially substituted monobromovaleranone (IR $\nu_{\text{max}} 1729\text{ cm}^{-1}$) with one mole of bromine also showed strong 1,3-diaxial interaction in the α -positions of the keto group in valeranone. Treatment of valeranone with an excess of bromine to furnish only a dibromoderivative (9) and the formation of only a monobenzylidene derivative (10) supported the IR data.

Ozonolysis of valerene (8) yielded a dialdehyde (11), which could be cyclised by treatment with alcoholic hydrochloric acid to an α, β -unsaturated aldehyde (12), thus providing proof in favour of the presence of a six membered ketone.

Hydrogen peroxide oxidation of the dialdehyde (11) gave the diacid (13), which could also be obtained either by the chromic acid oxidation of valeranone or by ozonolysis of the benzylidene derivative (10). The diacid (13), on pyrolysis, underwent cyclisation to afford norvaleranone (14), its IR $\nu_{\text{max}} 1735\text{ cm}^{-1}$ being indicative of the formation of a cyclopentanone ring.

The benzylidene derivative (15) of norvaleranone gave the diacid (16) which could only be converted to an anhydride (17). Bromination of (17) furnished the monobromoderivative (18), attempted dehydrobromination of which by treatment with collidine gave back the starting material. More drastic treatment with dimethylaniline at $140\text{--}190^\circ$ yielded two products, *viz.* trimethylphenylammonium bromide and the lactone anilide (19). These data indicated a part of the decalin system of valeranone to be constituted as (20).

Valeranone on selective photochemical cleavage yielded photovaleranoic acid (21), whose methyl ester could be subjected successively three times to Barbier-Wieland degradation to furnish trisnorphotovaleranoic acid (22). Formation of the acid (22) also showed that in valeranone a chain of three methylene groups was attached to the keto group. Dehydrogenation of (22) to give 1,2-dimethyl-4-isopropyl benzene (23) showed that the carboxyl group was attached to a quaternary carbon atom and valeranone could be represented by either (1) or (24).

Bayer-Villiger oxidation of valeranone gave a lactone (25), $\text{IR}\nu_{\text{max}}$ 1737 cm^{-1} (lactone $\text{C}=\text{O}$), which on alkaline hydrolysis and esterification with diazomethane gave the hydroxy ester (26). Dehydration of (26) gave a mixture of unsaturated esters (27), in which the exomethylene isomer was present at least to the extent of 50%. Ozonisation of the above mixture furnished the keto ester (28), $\text{IR}\nu_{\text{max}}$ $1711, 1748\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Bromination and dehydrobromination of (28) afforded the unsaturated keto ester (29), $\text{UV}\lambda_{\text{max}}$ $234\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.13); $\text{IR}\nu_{\text{max}}$ $1744, 1672, 1634\text{ cm}^{-1}$, ozonolysis of which followed by esterification yielded the keto diester (30). This reaction sequence fixed the position of the C_5 -methyl and that of the isopropyl group at C_7 , this being in agreement with the formula (1) for valeranone.

In the mixture of unsaturated esters (27), obtained by treating the hydroxy ester (26) with thionyl chloride in pyridine, the exomethylene isomer predominated. This could happen only if the hydroxyl group in (26) were equatorial⁵ and necessarily the methyl group axial. It may also be noted that the hydroxy ester (26) was obtained by Bayer-Villiger oxidation, which is known to proceed with the retention of configuration⁶, of valeranone,

via the lactone (25) which on treatment with boron trifluoride etherate furnished an isomerised lactone (31), IR spectra of the two lactones being different. The second lactone (31) was saponified, esterified and dehydrated to yield a mixture of unsaturated esters (32), which on ozonolysis followed by oxidation with nitric acid gave succinic and glutaric acids. In contrast, the unsaturated ester mixture (27) furnished only succinic acid, indicating the

presence of the angular substituent at C_{10} , which might have migrated during the formation of the second lactone, thus making the formation of glutaric acid feasible. This isomerisation was explained by Wagner-Meerwein rearrangement which required *trans*-antiparallel arrangement of the substituents involved, i.e., *trans* diaxial conformation of the lactonic oxygen and the C_{10} -angular methyl group. This led to the conclusion that the angular methyl groups were in *cis* relationship.

The NMR data⁷ also provided proof in favour of the *cis* fusion of the decalin ring system. The differences in the chemical shifts of $\text{C}_{10}\text{-CH}_3$ protons of coprostan-1-one and coprostanane and of cholestan-1-one and cholestanane were shown to be 0.20-0.212 and 0.360-0.384 p.p.m. respectively. The difference in the chemical shifts of $\text{C}_5\text{-CH}_3$ protons of valeranone and valerane was found to be 0.13 p.p.m.

Oxidation of valeranone with per acid in presence of a catalytic amount of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid afforded a hydroxy lactone (33). Dehydration and ozonisation of this lactone (33) gave 41.4% of formaldehyde. This indicated the position of the hydroxyl group to be on the isopropyl group, dehydration giving rise to an isopropenyl side chain. Considering that the isopropyl group was affected during the Bayer-Villiger oxidation, the close proximity of the isopropyl group to the keto group, i.e. 1,3-diaxial relationship (35), in valeranone at the time of the oxidation was assumed. This would fix the position of the isopropyl group at C₇ and *trans* relationship between the isopropyl and angular methyl groups.

Takemoto *et al.*⁸ had isolated valeranone and kanokonol (hydroxyvaleranone) from a number of Japanese valerians and studied their chemistry. Their investigations were of immense value in the establishment of the steric and absolute configuration of valeranone. They had also prepared the unsaturated keto ester (29) from valeranone *via* the keto ester (28) following the procedure described earlier, except that they obtained the pure exomethylene isomer (structure proved by IR and NMR data) of the unsaturated ester (27) by pyrolysis of the acetoxy derivative of the hydroxy ester (26). Next he proceeded to prepare the keto ester (28) and the unsaturated keto ester (29) from β -eudesmol (36) whose absolute configuration was well established⁹. Ozonolysis of β -eudesmol (36) followed by dehydration gave a mixture of two isomeric unsaturated ketones (37), which on hydrogenation yielded pure 14-noreudesmanone (38), homogeneity being proved by VPC and NMR spectrum. The β -configuration of the isopropyl group, i.e. its *cis* relationship with the angular methyl group, similar to that existing in eudesmol, was proved earlier by Woodward *et al.*⁹. The ketone (38) was converted into the hydroxy ester (39) in the usual way and the latter was oxidised to the keto ester (40). Comparison of physical data of (40) with those of the compound (28) proved their nonidentity. Bromination and debromination of (40) yielded an unsaturated keto ester (41) which was identical with the unsaturated keto ester (29) in all respects, except that it had an equal and opposite rotation, proving the two compounds to be enantiomers. Further, the ORD curves¹⁰ of the two compounds were found to bear the mirror-image relationship. The absolute configuration of (29) should therefore be represented by (42). The nonidentity of the compounds (40) and (28) can now be explained only

by difference in the steric relationship between the isopropyl and the angular methyl groups, which in the keto ester (28), derived from valeranone should be *trans* and its absolute configuration represented by (43), i.e. α -C₁₀ methyl and β -C₇ isopropyl.

The *cis* ring fusion and the α -configuration of angular methyl groups in valeranone received further confirmation from the study of the ORD data¹¹. It was observed that both *cis*-4 α -methyl-9 α -hexahydroindan-1-one (44) and *cis*-9 α -methyl-4 α -hexahydroindan-1-one (45) showed a negative Cotton effect. These results showed the sign of the Cotton curve was not dependent on the angular methyl groups in the *cis*-hexahydroindan-1-ones. A negative Cotton in the ORD curve was also shown by norvaleranone (14), and this led to the conclusion that angular methyl groups in valeranone were *cis* to each other and had α -configuration. Therefore, finally, valeranone was represented by the absolute configuration (1). The X-ray diffraction study¹² of the bromoanhydride of secovaleranoic acid (18) also supported this conclusion.

In view of the flexible nature of the *cis*-decalin system, valeranone can exist in two interchangeable all-chair conformations, the 'steroid' (46) and the 'nonsteroid' (47); in the latter the isopropyl group would be in the unfavourable axial conformation. The studies of the ORD data by Klyne *et al.*¹³ and Takemoto *et al.*¹⁴ have shed light on this point. The ORD curve of the 1-oxo-5-steroid (48), which represented *cis*-9-methyl-1-decalone, showed a negative Cotton effect and a high amplitude (α , -136). In the conformation (49) of the steroid (48), the carbonyl is attached to the neighbouring ring junction by an equatorial bond. Valeranone also exhibited negative Cotton effect and a high amplitude (α , -166) in

its ORD curve. It was, therefore, concluded that its carbonyl should be in an environment similar to that of the compound (48) and the 'steroid' *cis* conformation (46) was assigned to it.

The valeranes (50) are unusual among sesquiterpenes in two respects. Their carbon skeleton, although formally divisible into isoprene units, cannot be derived from farnesol, because two of the isoprene units must be linked in a tail to tail arrangement instead of the normal head to tail union to be found in the related hydronaphthalenes, *viz.*, the eudesmanes (51) and the cadinanes (52). The second distinctive feature of valeranes is their C_{10} absolute configuration which is opposite to that of most eudesmanes. A biogenetic scheme, accommodating these points, has been proposed by Parker *et al.*¹⁵ The intermediate (54), arising from the conformer (53), has been formulated as the precursor for the valerane group of sesquiterpenoids.

Two different groups of workers^{16,17,18} have confirmed the structure and configuration of valeranone by three different syntheses.

The first synthesis of Marshall *et al.*¹⁶ consisted of the conversion of (–)-carvomenthone (56) to *L*-valeranone, the enantiomer of natural *l*-valeranone. Condensation of (56) with

methyl vinyl ketone (55) furnished the ketol (57) which on dehydration afforded the octalone (58) of known stereochemistry¹⁹. Lithium aluminium hydride reduction, acetylation and hydrogenolysis with lithium in ethyl amine of the octalone (58) yielded the octalin (59) which on hydroboration²⁰ gave the decalol (60) in high yield. Oxidation of the decalol (60) with chromic acid furnished the decalone (61) which on equilibration yielded a nearly 1 : 1 mixture of the *cis* (62) and the *trans* (63) isomers, the equatorial *vs* axial orientation of the isopropyl side chain providing sufficient driving force to ensure a substantial predominance of the *cis*-isomer (63).

The *cis*-decalone (61) was also prepared independently by Theobald²¹. He obtained the ketol (66) by the condensation of (–)-dihydrocarvone (65) with 1-chlorobutan-3-one (64). The absolute configuration of the ketol (66) was proved by comparison of its ORD curve with that of the ketol (67) of known absolute configuration²². The saturated ketol, obtained by hydrogenation of the ketol (66), on treatment with ethanolic hydrochloric acid gave the unsaturated ketone (58). Desulphurisation of the thio-ketal (68) with Raney nickel furnished

the olefin (59), hydroboration of which gave a single crystalline alcohol (60) with the *cis* ring fusion. Oxidation of this alcohol (60) afforded the ketone (61), which, however, was found to be resistant to isomerisation by treatment with either dilute acid or dilute alkali.

Reduction of (61) with sodium in ethanol led to the formation of a new alcohol (69) which was different from the alcohol (60) only in the configuration of its hydroxyl group.

Comparison of the ORD curve of the ketone (61) with that of natural *D*-valeranone indicated the stereochemistry of the former to be enantiomeric to that of valeranone.

For introduction of the second angular methyl group, the keto methylene group of (61) was protected as the *n*-butylthiomethylene derivative and then methylated in presence of sodium hydride in dimethyl sulphoxide to obtain the compound (70). Removal of the blocking group in (70) furnished the ketone (71), whose identity was confirmed by direct comparison with valeranone.

Marshall *et al.*¹⁸ also reported a second stereoselective synthesis of *L*-valeranone. The *cis*-fused ketol (66), obtained by annelation reaction of dihydrocarvone (65) with methyl vinyl ketone (55), was hydrogenated to furnish the saturated ketol (57), lithium aluminium

hydride reduction of which afforded the diol (72). Monomethane sulphonate (73) of the diol, on treatment with potassium *t*-butoxide in *t*-butanol, underwent fragmentation to the butenyl-cyclohexanone (74). Treatment of the latter with methyl lithium furnished the tertiary alcohol (75) as a mixture of epimers which on treatment with formic acid yielded a mixture of isomeric formates (76 and 77). Saponification of the formate mixture followed by oxidation with chromic acid gave a mixture of ketones (78 and 79) which were separated by chromatography. The IR spectrum of the ketone (78) was identical with that of the enantiomer prepared from the natural (–)-valeranone. Bromination and dehydrobromination of the ketone (78) gave the octalone (80) which on treatment with lead tetraacetate yielded a mixture of the acetoxy ketone (81) and the dienone (82). Hydrogenation of the keto acetate (81) gave the dihydro compound (83), the thioketal (84) of which on treatment with lithium aluminium hydride afforded the alcohol (85). The alcohol (86) was obtained by desulphurisation of (85), and oxidation of the former furnished the ketone (71) identical with the previously reported sample. Alternatively, the keto acetate (83) was reduced with sodium borohydride to obtain the acetoxy alcohol (87) which on mesylation followed by treatment with a base gave a mixture of (+)-valeranone (16%) and the oxide (88) (84%). Reduction of the oxide (88) with lithium aluminium hydride furnished the decalol (85), the NMR spectrum of which was identical with that of the enantiomer prepared from natural valeranone.

A stereospecific synthesis of *l*-valeranone has been achieved by Wenkert and Berges¹⁷. Base catalysed condensation of *d*-carvomenthone (89) with 1,4-dimethoxy-2-butanone (90) gave a mixture of products from which the ketol (91) was isolated. Reduction of the ketol (91) with lithium in ammonia gave the demethoxy compound (92) which, on acid induced dehydration, furnished the unsaturated ketone (93). The ORD curve of the latter (93) was the mirror image of the known enantiomer. Base catalysed dehydration of the ketol (91) gave the unsaturated ketone (94), which on treatment with lithium aluminium hydride furnished the alcohol (95). The allylic alcohol (95) was subjected to Simmons-Smith reaction

to give the cyclopropane compound (96) which was oxidised with Jones' reagent to afford the ketone (97). Wolff-Kishner reduction of the ketone (97) yielded the tricyclic ether (98) which on hydrolysis with aqueous methanolic hydrochloric acid afforded *l*-valeranone identical in all respects with the natural product.

Recently, a stereoselective total synthesis of (\pm)-valeranone and one of its isomers, in which the isopropyl group is in *cis* relationship with the two angular methyl groups, has been achieved in our laboratory²³.

9-Hydroxy-10-methyl- Δ^4 -octalin-3-one (99) was the starting material of choice, and it was prepared according to the procedure of Boyce and Whitehurst²⁴ by the reduction of 10-methyl- Δ^4 -octalin-3,9-dione with purified sodium borohydride.

Initially our plan was to introduce an alkoxy carbonyl group at C-2 of the hydroxy unsaturated ketone (99), which could be later converted²⁵ to or replaced²⁶ by an isopropyl group.

Condensation of the hydroxy unsaturated ketone (99) with diethyl carbonate in presence of sodium hydride yielded a crystalline product, whose analytical data did not agree with those for the expected compound (100). It showed IR bands at 3650, 1656, 1626, 1527 and 1242 cm^{-1} and NMR signals at 1.4 δ (*t*, 3H), 1.9 δ (*m*, 4H), 2.3 δ (*s*, 3H), 2.8 δ (*m*, 4H), 4.3 δ (*q*, 2H), 7.5 δ (*s*, 1H) and 9.1 δ (*s*, 1H, disappears on deuteration), which were also not in conformity with the structure (100), but, were strongly indicative of the presence of an

aromatic ring which might have been formed by a base-catalysed rearrangement. Swaminathan *et al.*²⁷ had earlier observed that the vinyl carbinols (101) on treatment with a base rearranged to the dione (102). Consideration of a similar rearrangement of the condensation

product (100) in the present case, according to the mechanism indicated below, would lead to the formation of the compound (103). The analytical, IR and NMR data were also in excellent agreement with the structure (103), i.e., 2-carbethoxy-4-methyl-*ar*-tetralol.

The introduction of a carboxyl group at C-2 of the acetate of the compound (99) was next attempted by treating it with a solution of magnesium methyl carbonate in dimethylformamide. The product was worked up by the addition of a saturated solution of hydrogen chloride in methanol to obtain a crystalline product. The analytical data in this case also did not agree with the desired product (105). The IR bands at 3575, 2604, 1642, 1626, 1527 and 1220 cm^{-1} and NMR signals at 1.9 δ (*m*, 4H), 2.2 δ (*s*, 3H), 2.8 δ (*m*, 4H), 4.9 δ (*q*, 2H), 7.5 δ (*s*, 1H) and 8.9 δ (broad, 2H, disappears after deuteration) were again indicative of a phenolic carboxylic acid. Swaminathan and his associates²⁷ had also found that treatment of the enone alcohols (101) and the compound (99) with *p*-toluenesulphonic acid led to the formation of the rearranged dione (102) and 4-methyl-1-*ar*-tetralol (104) respectively. It was considered that in the present case the rearrangement of the condensation product (105) might have occurred during the work up involving acidification with a saturated solution of hydrogen chloride in methanol, and the formation of 2-carboxy-4-methyl-*ar*-tetralol (106) in accordance with the mechanism outlined below was envisaged. The analytical and physical data were in perfect agreement with the compound (106). Further, the ester (103) on hydrolysis yielded the acid (106).

Following our failure to introduce an alkoxy-carbonyl group at C-2 of the compound (99) and its acetate, the sequence of reactions for the synthesis was altered and the introduction of the second methyl group at C-5 was taken up. The copper catalysed conjugate

addition of methyl magnesium iodide to the compound (99) to obtain *cis*-5 β , 10 β -dimethyl-9 β -hydroxydecalin-3-one (107a) in 40% yield was reported by Rao *et al.*²⁸, the *cis*-fusion of the decalin ring being thoroughly proved. We repeated the experiment of Rao *et al.*²⁸, but failed to obtain the reported yield of the compound (107a) which we isolated as its acetate (107b). Next, the same conjugate addition in the presence of cupric acetate in tetrahydrofuran to the acetate of the compound (99) was carried out, when the pure 5 β , 10 β -dimethyl-9 β -acetoxydecalin-3-one (107b) was obtained in 55% yield. The acetoxy ketone (107b) was then condensed with an excess of diethyl carbonate in the presence of sodium hydride. The elemental analysis of the product, obtained in a very high yield, however, did not agree with the expected structure (108a). The IR spectrum, ν_{\max} 1730, 1724, 1653, 1626, 1242, 1227 cm^{-1} , was indicative of the presence of the β -keto ester group, but, NMR signals 1 δ (s, 3H), 1.19 δ (s, 3H), 1.8 δ (t, 6H), 4.5 δ (2q, 4H), 12.16 δ (s, 1H, disappears on deuteration) showed the presence of two ethoxycarbonyl groups and the absence of the acetoxy group. This could be explained by the replacement of the acetyl group at C-9 by an ethoxycarbonyl group by trans-esterification resulting from the reaction being carried out in an excess of diethyl carbonate, which had served also the purpose of a solvent. The analytical data

The above deliberations led us to consider the conversion of (108b) to (\pm)-valeranone through the following sequence : (i) reductive removal of the 3-keto group, (ii) treatment with methyl magnesium iodide or methyl lithium, (iii) oxidation of the C-9 hydroxyl, (iv) dehydration, (v) hydrogenation. It may be noted that the dehydration step might give rise to a mixture of olefines (116), and while hydrogenation of the isopropenyl isomer would lead exclusively to an isomer of valeranone (117), hydrogenation of the isopropylidene isomer was expected to yield a considerable amount of (\pm) valeranone (118), with the isopropyl *trans* to the methyls, as a result of hydrogenation from the convex side, i.e., from the same side of the methyl groups, of the folding *cis* decalin system.

For reduction of the 3-keto group, the crystalline ethylene thioketal (112) of the β -keto ester (108b) was prepared by treating the latter and ethanedithiol in glacial acetic acid with boron trifluoride etherate in fairly good yield. Desulphurisation of the thioketal (112) by treatment with Raney nickel in ethanol furnished the ethoxycarbonyloxy ester (113) also in very good yield. Interaction of the compound (113) with a large excess of methyl lithium gave the crystalline diol (114) in excellent yield; treatment with methyl magnesium iodide, however, gave a much inferior yield. Oxidation of the diol (114) with chromic acid pyridine complex furnished the hydroxy ketone (115). Heating of the compound (115) with potassium bisulphite under nitrogen, amongst other dehydration reactions carried out, gave a mixture of olefinic ketones, perhaps best represented by (116) on the basis of VPC analysis and IR and NMR spectral data, with the isoprenyl isomer predominating. Catalytic hydrogenation of this mixture (116) furnished a mixture of two saturated ketones (117) and (118) in the ratio of 1 : 4, as was evident from the VPC analysis. The retention time of the minor component was found to be identical with that of the natural valeranone³⁰

and the two were proved to be identical by the peak enrichment technique in the VPC. The major product could then only be the isomer (117), with the isopropyl group *cis* to the angular methyls, being formed mainly by hydrogenation of the isopropenyl isomer.

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